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Exotic lasers and vortex light beams

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ABSTRACT

Our research under ARIES focused on wakefield shaping using exotic laser beams as drivers. Our research uncovered a new intrinsic degree of freedom in plasma accelerators, the topology of plasma wakefields, which provides unprecedented control over the phase-space profile of relativistic bunches. We then showed that this control unlocked previously unrecognised superradiant x-ray emission regimes, which may be important in the context of spin-polarised positron production.

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

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	Name	Partner	Date
Authored by	J. Vieira, S. Dobosz Dufrenoy, Fabien Quéré	IST Lisbon, CEA/IRAMIS	18/05/20
Edited by	J. Vieira, S. Dobosz Dufrenoy, Fabien Quéré	IST Lisbon, CEA/IRAMIS	18/05/20
Reviewed by	A. Specka [WP coordinator]	CNRS	23/06/20
	M. Vretenar [Project Coordinator]	CERN	25/06/20
Approved by	Steering Committee		26/06/20

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Executive summary

We have investigated laser-plasma accelerators driven by exotic lasers with orbital angular momentum experimentally, theoretically and with simulations. Our experiments demonstrated that lasers with orbital angular momentum can drive relativistic plasma wakefields suitable for electron acceleration. However, experimental results also provided evidences about the occurrence of the filamentation instability during laser propagation. The laser filamentation instability amplifies initial laser intensity non-uniformities. Previous theory and simulations considered idealized scenarios where filamentation was absent. A further round of theoretical and simulation work is therefore required to understand the role of filamentation and its possible mitigation towards the generation of plasma waves suitable for positron acceleration. In addition to experiments, we showed theoretically and numerically that exotic lasers with orbital angular momentum (OAM) could be used to control the topology of laser-plasma accelerators. We discovered that laser pulses with helical intensity profiles can excite twisted plasma waves, which in turn can accelerate twisted electron bunches with collective orbital angular momentum. These bunches can relax the standard conditions to obtain superradiant emission in plasma accelerators. If brilliant gamma-rays produced with our method could be helpful in the generation of spin-polarised positron bunches will be the subject of future research. In parallel to this work on the use of laser beams carrying OAM, we have also investigated the optical properties of shaped laser pulse whose group velocity in vacuum can be continuously controlled. We have demonstrated such a velocity control experimentally, and the use of such pulses in laser-driven particle acceleration experiments is now an emerging research topic.

1. Introduction and Overview

This report pertains to task 18.3, LWFA with exotic laser beams, of ARIES Work-package 18, Very high gradient acceleration techniques. In this task we explored plasma accelerators driven by exotic lasers with orbital angular momentum. Our goal was to uncover new acceleration regimes potentially capable of delivering exotic electron bunches in compact plasma accelerators. Additionally, this research was also a critical step to propose a compact plasma based light source providing x-rays with unprecedented properties.

Purely analytical models for plasma-based accelerators, particularly plasma accelerators driven by exotic light, are currently based on simplified models with limited predictive capabilities. Thus, numerical simulations were critical to explore the physics self-consistently with little or few approximations. We have therefore set up the simulation framework to investigate plasma accelerators driven by twisted light and their corresponding radiation features.

We have covered a considerably broader area of research in comparison to our initial plan. We discovered that twisted lasers can be used to control the topology of the wakefield in plasma accelerators. Our work established the plasma wave topology as a fundamental degree of freedom in plasma acceleration, standing in equal footage to the plasma frequency or to the plasma wave amplitude. Controlling the wake topology can then be used to control phase-space properties of an accelerated particle bunch that otherwise remain inaccessible. As an illustration, we showed that

intense lasers with orbital angular momentum can drive twisted plasma waves to generate and accelerate electrons with quantized orbital angular momentum levels.

We then discovered that twisted electron bunches with angular momentum can relax the usual criteria underlying the generation of temporally coherent radiation. To demonstrate this, we developed a new radiation diagnostic tool for particle-in-cell codes. This tool was instrumental to investigate a generalised superradiance emission process. Twisted electron bunches provide a possible way to access generalised superradiance. Below, we provide a discussion about the usefulness of such scheme towards the generation of spin polarised positron bunches.

To complement our theory/simulation advances, we have performed the first experiments of plasma accelerators driven by exotic laser pulses at ultra-high intensities. These experiments showed that the propagation of intense lasers with orbital angular momentum can excite relativistic plasma waves, suitable for electron acceleration. Our experiments also showed that the laser pulse propagation is very likely subject to the filamentation instability. The filamentation instability amplifies initial non-uniformities on the transverse intensity profile of an intense laser. By only considering pure Laguerre-Gaussian modes, filamentation had not been previously foreseen in theory and simulations. It is thus likely that the occurrence and growth of filamentation has hindered the generation of doughnut shaped plasma waves, which are required for positron acceleration.

2. Plasma accelerators driven by exotic beams

1.1 LASER PLASMA ACCELERATION EXPERIMENTS DRIVEN BY EXOTIC BEAMS

Using plasmas to accelerate particles to high energies has long been identified as a promising path to obtain compact accelerators. In terms of particle energy, the most advanced scheme to date for electrons consists in using ultra-intense lasers or electron beam drivers to excite high amplitude ultra-relativistic waves in low density plasmas. Electrons trapped into these waves can gain energy and be accelerated to relativistic velocities.

The standard paradigm in laser-plasma acceleration relies on Gaussian laser pulses to drive the plasma. Gaussian beams can create a nonlinear electron plasma wave in the blowout regime. As a direct result of the nearly spherical shape that characterises the blowout regime, the wakefield provides linear focusing and accelerating fields for electrons. The usual, spherically shaped blowout regime, is, however, not adequate for positron acceleration. Instead of bringing positrons towards the axis, the transverse focusing force in the blowout regime defocuses positrons everywhere except in a narrow region where plasma electrons cross the axis at the back of the bubble.

By changing the spatial wakefield structure, higher order laser pulse modes provide promising pathways for positron acceleration [1]. Theory and simulations performed before the ARIES project had previously demonstrated that Laguerre-Gaussian laser beams with orbital angular momentum could excite a toroidal plasma wave with on-axis linear positron focusing and accelerating forces. These results provided a first major goal for our work under the ARIES project: to perform the first experiments of plasma accelerators driven by exotic light and demonstrate the existence of focusing and acceleration structures suitable for positrons in nonlinear plasma waves. We emphasize that the initial goal of these experiments was not yet to demonstrate positron acceleration, but rather to establish whether such accelerating structures can indeed be created, e.g. by observing their effects on electron beams. Injection and acceleration of positrons in such structures can only come as a second step in these experimental investigations.

An experimental set up has thus been devised at CEA Saclay using a helical phase plate to create a laser beam with OAM (see Fig. 1). In ideal experimental conditions, this should lead to a focus with a donut-shape intensity profile. However, collimated high-power laser beams are often affected by residual aberrations of the spatial phase, and can also feature complicated spatial intensity profiles. These beam imperfections unavoidably distort the intensity profile obtained at focus, where the laser-

Figure 1: Experimental setup at CEA Saclay to test LWFA with beam with OAM

plasma interaction occurs. As a result, the laser focal spot obtained with the helical phase plate deviated substantially from the expected donut shape. This is illustrated in Fig.2, which compares the focal spots obtained without (panel a) and with the helical phase plate (panel b). In the absence of the helical phase plate, the focal spot is close to a Gaussian profile, yet with some distortions due to residual beam aberrations (despite the use of an adaptive wavefront correction system). When the helical phase plate is inserted, the beam focus becomes closer to a donut, but this donut is far from ideal, and actually consists of two very clear asymmetric intensity lobes. This is a significant deviation from the conditions considered in simulations, and despite many attempts, we could not get closer to an ideal intensity donut in experiments. Propagation simulations have confirmed that this is due to residual imperfections of the laser beam prior to the helical phase plate, to which the structure of the intensity donut is very sensitive.

Figure 2: image of the focal spot obtained with UHI100 laser, at the focal plane, without (a) and with (b) an helical phase plate. The dot lines on the right part of the figure are just for eye guiding.

We have then investigated the properties of the relativistic electron beams produced when such shaped laser beams are used to drive a laser wakefield in an underdense plasma. A very encouraging result is that we did manage to observe accelerated electron beams with the helical phase plate inserted into the laser beam, despite the intensity loss that it unavoidably induces at focus. For about 50% of the shots, we observed two spatially-separated electron beams (see typical image on Fig.3), while a single electron beam is observed in the absence of the helical phase plate. The shaping of the laser thus has a clear effect on the accelerated electron beam.

However, this effect does not correspond to the one observed in simulations, where donut-shaped electron beams are produced. Our interpretation of this discrepancy is that that initial inhomogeneities in the laser beam intensity profile at focus get amplified during propagation in the plasma, through non-linear optical effects. Due to these non-linear effects, the two intense lobes observed in the laser focus get converted into two laser filaments, which thus drive two parallel plasma waves, where two laser wakefield acceleration processes occur independently. This would explain why two separate electron bunches are observed experimentally. According to this interpretation, the imperfections/inhomogeneities observed on the initial focus obtained with the phase plate thus prevent the excitation of the toroidal plasma waves observed in simulations, and this is why we do not observe donut shape electron beams. This clearly indicates that to pursue the use of OAM beams in laser wakefield experiments, significant efforts will have to be devoted to the improvement and control of the spatial quality of the high-power laser beams. Significant efforts are at present invested

in this task in the laser-plasma community, and there are thus good hopes that such experiments can be attempted in better conditions in the future.

Figure 3: typical image of the 2 electron beams obtained when the UHI100 laser beams was shaped by the phase plate

1.2 LASER BEAM INDUCED FILAMENTATION AS A POSSIBLE EXPLANATION FOR MULTIPLE BUNCHES.

To complement experiments, we performed additional theory studies to investigate the dynamics of exotic laser beams in plasma. We have thus generalized the standard self-focusing theory to incorporate the self-focusing of intense lasers with higher order Laguerre-Gaussian modes in plasma. The success of current laser-plasma acceleration experiments today largely depends on self-focusing. According to known theory, if the laser power is above the so-called critical power for self-focusing in plasma, the laser pulse can remain guided over distances that can largely exceed the Rayleigh length. Self-focusing thus provides a self-guided propagation regime that sustains plasma wakefields over the long distances required to effectively accelerate charged particles to relativistic energies.

The gradients on the plasma refractive index set the self-focusing properties of the plasma. In the presence of an intense laser, plasma electrons acquire a relativistic quiver motion in the laser fields, which cause an intensity-dependent change on the plasma refractive index. The laser self-focuses if the corresponding refractive index gradients are sufficiently strong. Expressions for the critical power for self-focusing in plasma were only known for Gaussian laser beams. We have therefore determined analytically the critical power for self-focusing in plasma as a function of the Laguerre-Gaussian radial and azimuthal indexes. Our theory showed that the critical power for self-focusing of laser beams increases with the orbital angular momentum [3]. This aspect should thus be considered when designing future experiments.

In parallel to purely analytical studies described above, we combined theory with advanced simulations to assess the potential of intense lasers with orbital angular momentum to shape the wakefield structure in laser-plasma accelerators. This work followed the installation of the plasma simulation code OSIRIS [2] in local computer clusters at Instituto Superior Técnico and in the TIER-0 computer cluster SuperMUC at the Leibniz research centre in Munich, Germany. We successfully

tested and used OSIRIS in these computing sites and demonstrated that it can be used to perform plasma acceleration simulations. We have also ensured that laser injection algorithms into the simulation can adequately model exotic lasers.

1.3 OPTICAL CONTROL OF THE TOPOLOGY OF LASER PLASMA ACCELERATORS

Currently, longitudinal phase-space properties of the accelerated bunches, such as their longitudinal momentum, can be effectively controlled. Despite recent progress to control the radial dynamics of the accelerated beams, obtaining control over the angular momentum degrees of freedom in plasma accelerators was not subject to previous research. Accessing them is however interesting from a fundamental perspective and important for applications, such as radiation generation as we will show.

To achieve control over the angular momentum degrees of freedom of relativistic electrons in plasma accelerators we focused on intense laser pulses with helical intensity profiles. These lasers are known as light springs [4]. Light springs can be expressed as a superposition of Laguerre-Gaussian modes, each with given amplitude and angular momentum. We found that under specific conditions, light springs can effectively generate twisted plasma waves, which carry orbital angular momentum themselves.

The wakefield structure of twisted plasma waves is rich. Just as in conventional, plane-wave like plasma waves, twisted plasma wakefields have accelerating and radial wakefield components. Twisted plasma waves, however, contain an additional azimuthal wakefield component, which is absent from plane-wave like plasma waves. The azimuthal wakefields can push electrons (and positrons) along the azimuthal direction. Therefore, trapped particles then execute a spiral trajectory as acceleration occurs. Close examination of the trajectory of trapped particles in twisted plasma waves revealed a surprising angular momentum quantisation rule. Leveraging on this interesting and novel feature, we found that twisted plasma waves can produce twisted electron bunches, which have a twisted current profile and carry a well defined angular momentum.

Figure 4 provides a summary of the main simulation results. It shows that the twisted wakefield structure can accelerate a helically modulated electron bunch (Fig. 4a). Figure 4b shows that twisted plasma wave contain an accelerating field component and Fig. 4c shows the novel azimuthal field component that follows from the twisted wakefield structure.

Additionally, we found that the laser dynamics in the twisted wakefield structures can be used to adjust the phase-velocity of electron plasma waves, and thus, the final energy gain of trapped electrons [5].

Fig. 4 Twisted plasma wakefields driven by a light spring moving in a preformed plasma doped with Nitrogen. (a) (right) Rainbow colors display the electric field of the light spring (LS). (left) blue-red isosurfaces show the twisted longitudinal electric field structure of the wake excited by this LS in the underdense plasma. These surfaces are not displayed for $x > 178c/\omega_p$ to avoid hiding the other plots. (middle) Spheres in rainbow colors correspond to ionization injected electrons from the inner (6^{th} - 7^{th}) shells of Nitrogen. (b)-(c) slices of the corresponding radial and azimuthal electric fields in the plasma. Field values are normalised to the cold wavebreaking limit $E_0 = m_e c \omega_p / e$.

3. Plasma accelerators driven by exotic beams: radiation signatures

1.4 RADIATION EMISSION TOOL

Particle codes for plasma acceleration simulations need to resolve the smallest relevant time and length scales over the typical macroscopic scales that correspond to the interaction times and distances required to observe acceleration and/or radiation emission processes. As a direct result, capturing the radiation properties from relativistic particles is computationally very expensive. This calls for the development of post-processing diagnostics that can retrieve radiation emission from the particle trajectories obtained from PIC simulations.

Radiation post-processing tools typically describe the radiation spectra associated with the motion of charged particles in plasma. This traditional approach provides data that can be directly compared with experiments, which also capture the radiation spectra. Even though experimental measurements cannot resolve them with present techniques, the spatiotemporal features of the radiation are an intrinsic and fundamental property of any radiated beam that remains nearly unexplored. One of the natural reasons is that tools to describe such features are not available.

Within ARIES, and with the goal of examining the radiation signatures of relativistic particles accelerated in particle accelerators driven by exotic light, we progressed towards the development of a post-processing diagnostic that can retrieve radiation emission from the trajectories of charged particles, known from particle simulations.

We have demonstrated the validity of our approach by comparing it against known theoretical results in standard synchrotron radiation configurations. Theoretical results are often expressed in the spectral domain. Our approach, instead, provides the spatiotemporal features. Expressing our spatiotemporal results as a function of radiation frequency is, however, straightforward and fast, requiring standard fast-Fourier transform routines. This methodology showed that our approach recovers known and consolidated theoretical results.

1.5 TEMPORALLY COHERENT RADIATION

The approach we took for the radiation post-processing diagnostic calculations captures temporal coherence effects by design. We have thus used our tool to find signatures of temporal coherence effects in the context of our workpackage in ARIES, by considering the motion of electron bunches with angular momentum, as produced in twisted plasma accelerators. We have found that these bunches may significantly relax the conditions to obtain temporal coherent emission. This may become a very exciting and promising advance. Our work is currently accepted for publication in Nature Physics [7].

Superradiance is at the heart of today's most advanced light sources. Superradiance, a classic concept introduced by Robert Dicke in 1954, is the anomalous radiance describing coherent photon emission from a collection of light-emitting particles. Initially proposed in the context of atomic physics, superradiance provides valuable insights into quantum electrodynamics and quantum communications, astrophysics and advanced light sources. Superradiant emission leads to intense photon beams where the intensity goes as the number of particles squared. This result is intuitively expected when the distance between light-emitting particles is much smaller than the photon wavelength — as originally proposed in the seminal work by Dicke, and being also the regime of operation of free electron lasers. Our work breaks this natural assumption: by focusing on the radiation from a relativistic particle beam with angular momentum, we predicted a superradiant emission regime that holds even when the particle number per photon wavelength vanishes (see Fig. 5a).

Individual particles from a charged particle bunch with angular momentum under the action of an external field (e.g. radial focusing force in a plasma pure ion channel) execute helical trajectories. As a result, and just as the light spring that propagates in a focusing parabolic plasma channel, the helically modulated bunch (see e.g. Fig. 5a) also performs a helical motion. The corresponding phase-like velocity of the modulations are set by the temporal pitch of the helix and by the frequency of the oscillation. Hence, and just like a cork-screw, these modulations may appear to move forward or backward within the bunch. The speed at which these modulations propagate throughout the bunch is a result of a purely collective effect. As a result, these modulations can propagate at any velocity. For example, these modulations appear to travel instantaneously if the temporal pitch of the bunch helical profile would tend to infinity.

The transition from sub-luminal to super-luminal motions leads to a novel superradiant emission mechanism. We found that this transition leads to the generation of an optical shock that moves along the Vavilov-Cherenkov radiation angle (see Fig. 5b). The Vavilov-Cherenkov condition cannot be satisfied in vacuum for a single particle because no single particle can travel faster than c . We found this no longer holds if we take the collective motions of a bunch instead. By suitably changing the temporal pitch of the helical bunch, we found that it is possible to satisfy the Vavilov-Cherenkov radiation angle condition along any direction, for arbitrary photon velocities, and in vacuum.

This aspect is important because obtaining superradiance in a non-dispersive medium as vacuum (or a pure ion channel, as ions will not move under the action of x-rays) (see Fig. 5c) allows to concentrate broadband radiation into the shortest possible duration as allowed by the uncertainty principle.

This process can work in any spectral domain. We have demonstrated its effectiveness in the context of x-ray generation, but the generalized superradiance mechanism can also be applied in the generation of temporally coherent gamma rays. Producing circularly polarized gamma rays is important in the context of spin-polarized positron production. We are, however, uncertain that our scheme could be effectively used for this purpose. The radiation that is produced through this generalized superradiant emission mechanism is intrinsically broad-band. It is therefore likely that different spectral components of the radiation will have different polarizations. We anticipate this may reduce the spin-polarisation of relativistic positrons generated from such a gamma source. Additional research thus needs to be undertaken in order to explore the level of circular polarization of the radiation produced in generalized superradiance and its effectiveness to the generation of spin-polarized positron bunches.

Fig. 5 (a) Concept: a sinusoidally shaped particle beam moves along x in a focusing force. The modulation wavelength is several orders of magnitude larger than the radiation wavelength. Crests (and troughs) move faster than c even though each beam particle is sub-luminal. Radiation is spatially and temporally coherent at the Vavilov-Cherenkov cone-angle θ . (b) Emitted radiation intensity distribution in a virtual plane detector showing superradiant photon beams in the cone-angle θ . Time normalised to the particle frequency of oscillation ω_0 . (c) Radiation peak intensity grows quadratically with propagation distance, i.e. quadratically with the number of particles contributing to the radiation.

4. Ultrashort pulses with controlled velocity

In parallel to the work described above on laser beams with OAM, we have also identified an optical scheme that can generate laser intensity peaks with controllable and adjustable velocity in vacuum [6]. We have nicknamed this scheme the ‘sliding focus’. Such a control on the pulse velocity could obviously prove extremely useful for laser-driven particle acceleration, for instance by facilitating the injection of charges in the accelerating plasma structure thanks to gradually-accelerating laser pulses, or by providing a way to mitigate dephasing of charges in this accelerating structure. This scheme has so far been investigated for laser beams propagating in vacuum, and future studies will aim at extending these investigations to the more complex case of propagation in underdense plasmas.

This control on the velocity of the pulse peak intensity is achieved by inducing a combination of longitudinal chromatism and temporal chirp on the laser beam. We have carried out a detailed theoretical analysis, which is described in [6]. We have then designed a special doublet lens to generate such beams, and tested this optic by using recently-developed spatio-temporal measurement techniques. Using this optic on the UHI100 high-power femtosecond laser at CEA-Saclay, we have been able to demonstrate the sliding focus effect experimentally (Fig.6) [8]. We note that similar investigation have been carried out almost simultaneously in USA (LLE, Rochester), where this scheme has been nicknamed the ‘flying focus’ [9]. They successfully implemented this effect experimentally using a diffractive lens, while we have used refractive lens.

Numerical studies of laser wakefield electron acceleration with such beams are in preparation. We have already included these lasers in the OSIRIS simulations and explored their evolution in vacuum, confirming that there is a large flexibility to control the velocity of the peak of the intensity of these beams. The new simulation tool is fully operational in 2D geometries and is ready to explore the self-consistent evolution of these beams in the plasma for the first time.

Figure 6: Measured velocity (a) and pulse duration (b) of the intensity peak formed by a shaped laser beam in the flying/sliding focus scheme, as a function of chirp applied on the pulse, for two different magnifications of the imaging system (see text), $M = 1$ and $M = 3$. The shaping has here been induced using a refractive chromatic doublet, and the chirp was controlled by moving one of the gratings in the compressor

5. Future plans / Conclusion / relation to other ARIES work

The ARIES project enabled us to make significant advances regarding the usefulness of exotic lasers in plasma-based accelerators and light sources. Our advances were in experiments and in theory. We experimentally demonstrated the generation of intense Laguerre-Gaussian laser pulses and investigated how these beams accelerated electrons in a laser-plasma accelerator. Despite obtaining electron acceleration, our experiments have also showed the effect of filamentation induced by initial laser intensity non-uniformities, which appear due to the presence of multiple higher order modes. This prevented the acceleration of a ring bunch of electrons, as predicted in simulations. Thus, further theoretical and simulation work needs to be undertaken in order to evaluate the role of the filamentation instability in experiments and potential mitigation strategies. The experiments have been performed on UHI100 before shutting down the facility during 2019. Since then, the whole experimental ensemble has been redesigned and will be rebuilt few kilometers away from the initial location, in a new refurbished experimental area (CEA-Orme des Merisiers), however most likely not before the end of ARIES. This will be an opportunity to try again the generation of exotic electron beam from structured laser beam, as we should gain between 30-40% energy on the laser beam due to an optimized beam line transport. This was identified as a limitation for the experiment, as well as inhomogeneities in the laser spatial beam profile.

In parallel to experiments, we have also deepened our theoretical understanding of laser plasma accelerators driven by exotic light. We demonstrated that these lasers can effectively control the topology of laser plasma accelerators. This control is important because the topology directly defines the wakefield structure in the plasma, which in turn establishes the phase-space properties of the relativistic particles produced in plasma accelerators. We showed that lasers with orbital angular momentum could generate twisted plasma waves producing helical electron bunches.

We showed that these bunches can relax the standard criteria to obtain temporally coherent x-rays. This is interesting in the scope of ARIES because it opens a new pathway towards brilliant gamma ray sources that could potentially enable spin-polarized positron production. However, further research is still required in order to access the viability of the generalized superradiance mechanism we discovered to the purpose of generating spin-polarized positron bunches.

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